

Using Models of the Human Visual System in the Design of Stack Filters for the Enhancement of Color Images

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ABSTRACT

A technique is developed for utilizing models of the Human Visual System to improve the design of filters for the enhancement of color images. The technique uses an image fidelity measure based on models of the human visual system – such as the Visible Differences Predictor (VDP) - in a nested loop training algorithm. In the inner loop of the algorithm, a stack filter is trained under a Weighted Mean Absolute Error (WMAE) Criterion to remove noise. In the outer loop, the VDP is used to train the weights in the WMAE criterion to ensure that the filter to which the algorithm converges is one that produces output images that are as visually satisfying as possible.

The stack filters resulting from this VDP-driven, WMAE approach perform much better than filters trained under the standard mean absolute error criterion. This fact is demonstrated with color images. The robustness of these trained filters to variations in both the image and the noise is discussed.

1 Introduction

Stack filters are a class of discrete-time, nonlinear filters that are defined by two properties [1]: the weak superposition property known as the threshold decomposition [2, 3], and the ordering property called the stacking property. One of the main strengths of stack filters is the existence of an analytical technique for determining a stack filter which is optimal for estimation under the Mean Absolute Error (MAE) criterion [4, 5, 6, 7, 8].

One difficulty with this theory of MMAE stack filtering is that it yields filters that don't always produce the desired *visual* result in image processing applications. The hypothesis motivating this paper is that this difficulty is due to the error criterion that is used, not to any fundamental limitations of stack filters. The problem is that the MAE criterion simply does not assign the same level of significance as the human visual system to certain types of noise artifacts.

A new stack filter design algorithm is therefore proposed. It is based upon a Weighted Mean Absolute Error (WMAE) criterion instead of the MAE criterion,

which assigns the same weight to all errors. The weights in the WMAE criterion are designed with the aid of the Visible Differences Predictor (VDP) [9], which can estimate the sensitivity of the human visual system to changes in images. We do not use all of the information in the visible difference probability image produced by the VDP; instead, we threshold the VDP output image, add up all entries in the map that exceed a threshold and use the resulting number as a perceptual error measure. This perceptual error measure is computed after each adaptation of the weights in the WMAE.

As shown in Figure 1, the two images used in this computation are the desired image and the output obtained when a stack filter designed with the current setting of weights in the WMAE is applied to the corrupted version of the desired image. This measure determines if further change in the weights in the WMAE criterion are necessary. This new algorithm eventually determines weights for the WMAE criterion which correspond to a global minimum for the perceptual error measure. Any stack filter which minimizes this optimal WMAE criterion will therefore minimize the perceptual error measure.

2 Overview of the New Algorithm

In this new approach, the filtering of the image takes place in two stages. In the first stage, the goal is to use a stack filter $S_{f_1}(\cdot)$ based on the positive Boolean function $f_1(\cdot)$ to remove noise that is positive-going; the filter $S_{f_2}(\cdot)$ in the second stage removes negative-going noise. Smaller windows can be used for each of these procedures than would be required if the filter were to remove noise of both signs simultaneously. To achieve the desired visual effects, the weights in the mean absolute error criterion used to design the two filters are modified so the criterion more closely matches a perceptual error criterion.

The modifications made to the error criterion concern the weights assigned to the errors made for each observation vector. In the (unweighted) MAE criterion, all errors are assigned an equal weight of 1.0. There is complete freedom, though, in how these weights can be

Figure 1: Block diagram of optimal adaptive two-stage stack filtering algorithm with error weights selected via the VDP algorithm.

assigned. We have chosen to allow each weight to take any value between 0 and 1, and to select the weights independently for each type of error.

Consider the first stage filter, whose goal is to suppress positive-going noise. The weights corresponding to negative-going errors are chosen to be less than 1.0, while those for positive-going errors are left equal to 1.0. If the difference between these two weights is large enough, the resulting filter almost completely suppresses positive-going noise impulses. If the difference is too large, though, the filter designed with this error criterion will *introduce* more negative-going noise.

Once the first stage filter has been designed, the second stage filter is designed to remove the negative-going noise from the output of the first-stage filter. The techniques used to choose the weights in the error criterion for this filter are the same as those for the first-stage filter.

By using a two-stage filtering procedure, and modifying the error weights for each stage, we have found that filters of smaller window size can be used while still achieving dramatically better visual results. A cascade of two 4x4 filters designed this new way can be trained and applied to an image in 2 minutes on a Sparc 5, and the resulting filter will outperform one-stage stack filters with the largest window for which training is feasible (5x5).

The weights in this Weighted Mean Absolute Error (WMAE) criterion are designed with the aid of the Visible Differences Predictor (VDP), which can estimate the sensitivity of the human visual system to changes in images. The VDP algorithm feeds back the *visual* error to the two-stage stack filtering to adjust the weights until the filter is reached or near optimal based on *visual* criterion. Figure 1 illustrates the procedure used for the two-stage filtering algorithm. Note the use of the VDP algorithm to provide guidance in choosing the weights in the WMAE criterion.

Figure 2: Convergence behavior of *visual* error metric of 4 x 4 weighted stack filter with VDP algorithm.

3 Experimental Results

In this section, the filtering behavior of the new cascaded filter is examined for color images. The results are obtained by variation of the error weights. Figure 2 shows an example of the convergence behavior of the *visual* error metric when the full training algorithm described above is executed. The experimental results show that visual error converges to the global minimum. Note that there are several local minima in the graphs. They occur when a reduction in the weights in the WMAE causes the filter to destroy more detail even though it is removing more noise. This phenomenon can actually be observed in the sequence of filtered images resulting from the algorithm.

The color test image we used for the new algorithm is the YUV color image “Salesman”. Impulse and/or line drop-out noise is added to each component of the color image independently to produce a noisy version of the image. Because of the vector structure of multivariate stack filters and image format consideration, the noise

is added in each component of the RGB colorspace independently and the stack filters are also operated in RGB colorspace. The window size used for both filtering stages in the MMAE and WMAE stack filters is 4 x 4.

Figure 3(a) is the original image of Salesman and Figure 3(b) is the noisy image that will be filtered by the new algorithm. Figure 3(c) shows the result of applying the MMAE filtering algorithm. Figure 3(d) shows the results of applying the new algorithm with the best choice for the WMAE criterion. Note that the MMAE error method leaves a large number of annoying artifacts in the output image. The output of the WMAE, VDP-driven approach is essentially free of all impulsive and line drop-out noise, despite the high occurrence probability of the noise. Overall, the new filtering algorithm outperforms all other methods we have found in the literature for this type of noise. Also, examination of the MAE and WMAE based approaches shows that the VDP-driven WMAE approach strikes a very good balance between detail preservation and noise attenuation.

4 Conclusion

In this paper, we presented a minimum WMAE stack filtering algorithm which uses the visual differences predictor to achieve better performance in image processing applications than that achieved by the minimum MAE stack filtering approach. The new algorithm retains the iterative nature of the present adaptive minimum MAE algorithm but it allows the weights of the error criterion to vary during the training process. We also derived a visual error metric which served as the guiding metric for weight adaptation in the WMAE criterion. Through the experimental results, we verified that the visual error of the algorithm decreases to a minimum, at which point the algorithm produces a stack filter which is optimal in both the WMAE sense and the perceptual sense.

Many tests have been carried out to determine the robustness of the filters produced by this new HVS-model driven approach to designing stack filters for image enhancement. While there is not sufficient space to provide these examples, the general conclusion from the experiments is that good performance can be maintained by training with images that are as detailed as the most detailed image expected in the target set of images and with slightly heavier noise than is expected in the target set of images. This approach removes all noise and introduces only slightly more blurring of the image than is obtained with filters designed for each specific image from the target image set.

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(a)	(b)
(c)	(d)

Figure 3: (a) The original color image of Salesman. (b) Original plus independent 10% two-sided, additive impulsive noise with amplitude 200, and with line drop-outs of average length 5 and occurrence probability .005, on each component of colorspace (YUV). (c) Output of stack filter designed using original MMAE method applied on each component. (d) Output of stack filtering operation designed with new Weighted MAE method applied on each component.